

StArt - State of the Art through Systematic Review

Title: Genetic resistance of *Musa* spp. to phytoparasitic nematode species: a systematic review

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Description: This article is a systematic review of studies carried out over the last thirteen years on the existing banana breeding methods to aid the management and control of nematodes in banana and plantain crops.

Objectives: To systematically gather and review research from the last thirteen years on the use of genetic improvement for resistance to banana parasitic nematodes.

Main Question:

- Q1. What are the main nematode species that affect banana and plantain crops?
- Q2. Which cultivars are recognized as resistant to nematodes?
- Q3. Which banana breeding programs are focused on nematode resistance or cross-breeding for the purpose of developing resistant cultivars?
- Q4. Are there any known sources of nematode resistance?
- Q5. Which genes have been reported to be related to nematode resistance?
- Q6. How is germplasm selected?
- Q7. What are the most used methodologies for extracting nematodes from roots?
- Q8. What are the methods for assessing symptoms?
- Q9. What existing tools are used to characterize nematode-resistant plants? Are there any molecular markers?
- Q10. Are there any studies on the topics of gene editing, cisgenics, and transgenics?
- Q11. How often is the banana genome used?

Keywords: *Musa* spp., genetic resistance, parasitic nematodes, phytonematodes.

Source Selection Criteria: Only scientific articles.

Studies Languages: Only English.	
Source Search Methods: Papers found in widely available scientific databases.	
Source Engine: Google Scholar, Springer, PubMed Central, CAPES Journal Portal, Web of Science, Scopus and MusaLit	
Studies inclusion (I) and exclusion criterias (E):	(I) articles that answer the protocol's questions (E) duplicate articles; (E) articles that were not in line with the objectives of our work; (E) review articles; (E) works not written in english; (E) theses, dissertations, manuals, book chapter, articles published in conference proceedings; (E) articles published before 2011.
Studies types definition:	Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
Initial studies selection:	Papers that contain in the title, abstract or keywords, the terms (" <i>Musa</i> spp." OR bananas OR plantains) AND (nematodes OR "plant parasitic nematodes" OR phytonematodes)
Studies quality evaluation:	The objectives and criteria of inclusion and exclusion were previously defined, without ambiguity. Exclusions os papers based on the characteristics/sources of the studies were appropriate. To reduce bias risk, the PRISMA checklist was inserted.
Information Extraction Fields:	Country of study; type of test applied; genes; techniques and tools; resistance sources; biotechnology.
Results Summarization: In the form of graphs, tables, bibliometric maps and word cloud.	